

Purchase Intention Model: Perceived Value, Service Quality and Store Environment (Case Study at Sociolla in Pandemic)

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Abstract:- This study aims to evaluate how service quality, store environment, and perceived value influence purchase intention. Customers that visited the Sociolla offline store in Lippo Mall Puri during the pandemic are the focus of this study. This study was conducted with 240 customers who had visited Sociolla Lippo Mall Puri. The research method applied is quantitative descriptive research. The data analysis used is SEM analysis using the Smart PLS application. The study's findings indicate that service quality has a direct impact on perceived value and purchase intention. The store environment influences perceived value and purchase intention significantly. Perceived value holds a partial mediating effect between service quality and purchase intention. Moreover, perceived value partially mediates the relationship between store environment and purchase intention.

Keywords:- Service Quality, Store Environment, Perceived Value, Purchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

In 2018, the national cosmetics industry, which includes beauty and personal care products, grew by 20%, which was four times the growth rate of the national economy in 2017. This increase in growth to double digits was driven by huge demand from the domestic and export markets as people's trends began to shift and they began to pay more attention to their primary need for body care products [1].

The Central Statistics Agency reported that the import value of beauty products, including cosmetics, care products, and soap, increased by 31.7% from January to July of 2017 to \$431,2 million in 2018 [2]. John Marco Rasjid, chief executive officer (CEO) of Social Bella, stated that Indonesians continue to spend an average of \$20 per capita on cosmetics and personal care products. This figure is less than that of Thailand (\$56 per person) and Malaysia (\$75 per person) [3]. The growth forecast for the Beauty and Personal Care Market in Indonesia until 2023 is provided below [4].

Ditopang Usia Muda

PASAR produk perawatan dan kecantikan menjadi salah satu pasar dengan pertumbuhan tercepat di Indonesia, khususnya segmen kosmetik dan perawatan kulit. Faktor utama untuk pertumbuhan ini adalah pergeseran generasi dengan masuknya konsumen muda ke pasar kosmetik. Perubahan ini diperkuat oleh media sosial dan e-commerce yang memiliki efek pada perilaku pembelian produk kecantikan.

Nilai Ekspor Produk Kosmetik Indonesia (US\$ juta)

Total penjualan kosmetik, skincare, personal care, fragrance (US\$ juta) Rata-rata belanja kosmetik per kapita (US\$) Pertumbuhan penjualan (%)

Kanal Penjualan (%)

Fig 1. Growth of the Beauty and Personal Care Market in Indonesia in 2015 – 2023

Source: Koran Tempo, 2021

Figure 1 shows data from the Ministry of Industry indicating that the market for beauty and personal care products in Indonesia increased to US\$ 6.9 billion in 2019. In 2023, this amount is projected to increase to \$8.5 billion. Both offline and online sales channels are anticipated to experience growth in revenue. In 2019, the offline sales percentage reached 83%, while the online sales percentage reached 17%. With the development of the internet, it is anticipated that by 2023, the percentage of online sales will increase to as much as 40%.

Before the COVID-19 pandemic, all predictions for the growth of the beauty and personal care market were made. In the era of the COVID-19 pandemic, the beauty industry has

become a stable-growing industry that has been able to withstand multiple economic downturns [5]. Expansion of marketing for beauty and personal care products through digital channels, as well as increasing the number of customers willing to pay a premium for superior quality.

In numerous ways, the COVID-19 pandemic presents never-before-seen obstacles. It endangers the lives of millions of people worldwide. In addition, social distancing guidelines implemented to contain the virus have a disproportionate impact on the service sector, where physical proximity is frequently crucial. Due to social distancing guidelines, there were very few opportunities for offline sales during the pandemic (Csiszárík-Kocsir et al., n.d.).

Fig 2. Retail Sales Growth Graph Indonesia October 2019 – March 2021

Source: Ceicdata.com, 2021

As shown in the above graph, retail sales experienced a significant decline in purchasing power compared to online sales. During the COVID-19 pandemic, Alphonsus Widjaja (2020), the General Chairperson of the Indonesian Shopping Center Management Association (APPBI), stated that limiting the operating hours of shopping centers had a significant impact on the number of visits. The decrease in visits has an effect on the level of sales [8]. The decline in people's purchasing power affected the retail industry's performance. Roy Mandey (2020), chairman of the Indonesian Retailers Association (Aprindo), estimates that the retail industry will grow by only 3-3.5% in 2020. This number is more than halved compared to the 8-8.5% growth recorded by the retail industry in 2019. The results of Bank Indonesia's Retail Sales Survey for April 2020 confirm this. The Real Sales Index (IPR), which registered a value of minus 16.9%, reflected the overall decline in retail sales. This number is lower than the IPR for March 2020, minus 4.5 percent [9].

Social Bella (Sociolla), which was founded in 2015 and is one of the leading beauty techs in Indonesia, has evolved into a beauty e-commerce that caters to the needs of Indonesian women. In collaboration with more than 200 beauty brands, Sociolla consistently fulfills its mission to increase beauty enthusiasts' access to authentic, BPOM-certified beauty products [10]. In 2020, in the midst of the

COVID-19 pandemic, Sociolla dared to open ten offline stores in five Indonesian cities. Chrisanti Indiana, co-founder and chief marketing officer of Social Bella Indonesia, stated that the opening of the new store demonstrates the resilience of Sociolla's business during the pandemic, which is supported by an integrated ecosystem, technology, and a profound understanding of Indonesian consumers. The opening of ten new Sociolla stores demonstrates Sociolla's dedication to providing beauty enthusiasts with a comprehensive and enjoyable shopping experience [11].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Economic of Natural Disaster Behavior*

According to [12], disasters have a different set of effects on the economy than other economic phenomena, such as changes in public policies and/or regulations, and often necessitate the careful management of changes in economic behavior under the chaos of the post-disaster situation. There are both direct and indirect economic effects of natural disasters. Examples of direct economic losses include the destruction of housing, businesses, productive capital, infrastructure, crops, and livestock, as well as (monetization) physical and mental health impacts (Botzen et al., 2019). Indirect effects include both short-term and long-term economic production and consumption losses, as well as any associated economic recovery path (Kousky, 2014). [15], cited in [16], reveals that

certain disaster shocks, such as climate disasters such as droughts, extreme temperature events, hurricanes, and floods, can have a substantial effect on GDP per capita. Disasters have a substantial effect on shopping habits. The most recent pandemic is COVID-19, which has affected every aspect of life. It alters people's purchasing preferences and alters their behavior, and it has sought more conscientious ways to meet needs (Csiszárík-Kocsir et al., n.d.).

➤ *Purchase Intention*

Alatas & Tabrani (2018) discovered that purchase intention is a behavioral component of consumption attitudes, where purchase intention is an individual or consumer activity directly involved in acquiring and utilizing the offered products. Pradana et al. (2020), purchase intention typically begins with one's knowledge of a product, which influences one's attitude of intention to buy the product. This purchase intention creates motivation that persists in the minds of consumers and develops into a strong desire, so that when a consumer has to fulfill his needs, he will act on what is in his mind.

➤ *Perceived Value*

Hong & Brahmana (2015), define customer perceived value as the result of a customer's evaluation of benefits versus costs as an alternative. This means that when a customer enjoys a service at a certain cost, it is deemed valuable because acquiring similar services from other providers would require greater sacrifice. Customer perceived value is the difference between a customer's perspective evaluation of all benefits and

overall costs in comparison to existing alternatives and the customer's evaluation of all benefits and costs from the vendor's perspective (Kotler and Keller, 2016).

➤ *Service Quality*

Lovelock dan Wright (2007), cited in Hadibrata et al. (2018), emphasized that service quality is the expected quality and quality control in order to meet customer requirements. Vierdwiyani & Syafarudin (2020), The quality of service can be determined by comparing consumer perceptions of the service they actually receive or get to the service they actually expect or desire for the company's service. Hardiansyah (2011) in Buchori & Harwani (2021) defines quality of service as an assessment of service quality as a global consideration or attitude related to service excellence.

➤ *Store Environment*

Hanaysha (2018), state that store environment refers to the atmosphere or atmosphere of a particular store where customers purchase products or services, and it consists of tangible and intangible attributes that facilitate interaction between service providers and customers. [24] Store environment is a socially constructed reality composed of physical and social elements, and consumers' perceptions of the store can be based on physical and social cues that are represented symbolically in their minds. Similarly, Baker et al., (2002) in Mostafa & Elseidi (2021), where the variables in the store environment are ambience, design, and social interaction, found that the store environment influences consumer behavior.

Fig 2 Structural Relationship
Source: Picture of research (2021)

- H₁ : Service quality will positively and significantly affect perceived value
- H₂ : Store environment will positively and significantly affect perceived value
- H₃ : Perceived value will positively and significantly affect purchase intention
- H₄ : Service quality will positively and significantly affect purchase intention

- H₅ : Store environment will positively and significantly affect purchase intention
- H₆ : Perceived value will mediate the relationship between service quality and purchase intention
- H₇ : Perceived value will mediate the relationship between store environment and purchase intention

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The study population consists of Sociolla consumers who have visited the Lippo Mall Puri retail location. A total of 240 panelists were selected using a non-probability sampling method. The data collection method used is to distribute an electronic questionnaire using Google Forms and a Likert scale as a measurement scale. The five-point Likert scale ranges from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree." The analysis technique employed is SEM with SMART PLS. Two stages of testing or measuring the model are performed in the use of SEM analysis in the SMART PLS application: the outer model and the inner model [27].

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Based on data from 240 respondents, it shows that the majority of Sociolla customers 93,3% are women and as many as 30.8% are between 25-35 years old. The majority of respondents are S1 graduates 54.2%. The descriptive results show that majorly 55% of respondents have jobs as private employees. As many as 41.7% of the panel involved in the research earned more than five million rupiah a month. Furthermore, 50% of respondents have spending money range one million five hundred thousand rupiah to one million five hundred thousand rupiah for beauty care in a month.

➤ *Outer Model Test*

In evaluating each construction, convergent validity is taken into consideration. Using outer loading and AVE (Average Variance Extracted) parameters, convergence validity is determined. Individual reflective sizes are said to correlate with the structure being measured when the value is greater than 0.70. For early-stage research, however, a measurement scale with a factor load value between 0.5 and 0.6 is considered adequate [28].

Table 1 Average Variance Extracted (AVE) Test Result

Variable	Condition	AVE
Purchase Intention (Y)	> 0.5	0.663
Perceived Value (Z)	> 0.5	0.647
Service Quality (X1)	> 0.5	0.677
Store Environment (X2)	> 0.5	0.796

Source: Data of Research (2021)

After validity testing, reliability testing is carried out by looking at alpha cronbach values as well as composite reliability. The reliability test results show that the research model is reliable.

Table 2 Reliability Test Result

Variable	Condition	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability
Purchase Intention (Y)	> 0.6	0.751	0.854
Perceived Value (Z)	> 0.6	0.818	0.879
Service Quality (X1)	> 0.6	0.905	0.926
Store Environment (X2)	> 0.6	0.872	0.921

Source: Data of Research (2021)

Furthermore, discriminant validity checking is performed with Fornell-Larcker Criterion test. Discriminant validity is good if the squared value of the AVE root for each structure has a correlation value that is greater than the correlation with other structures. The results show that the AVE root for each construct measured is greater than the correlation score between that construct and the other constructs in the model. Therefore, discriminant validity between constructs is achieved.

Table 3 Fornel-Larcker Criterion Test Results

	Perceived Value	Purchase Intention	Service Quality	Store Environment
Perceived Value	0.804			
Purchase Intention	0.668	0.814		
Service Quality	0.739	0.743	0.823	
Store Environment	0.656	0.684	0.686	0.892

Source: Data of Research (2021)

➤ *Inner Model Test*

Internal model analysis is carried out with the aim of ensuring that the built structure model is robust and accurate. The testing of the structural model is carried out by looking at the R-Square value which is the Goodness-Fit model test.

Table 4 Goodness of Fit Test Result

Variable	R ²	Q ²	f ²
<i>Purchase Intention</i>	0.623	0.406	
<i>Perceived Value</i>	0.587	0.367	
<i>Service Quality</i> → <i>Perceived Value</i>			0.382
<i>Store Environment</i> → <i>Perceived Value</i>			0.102
<i>Service Quality</i> → <i>Purchase Intention</i>			0.179

Variable	R ²	Q ²	f ²
Store Environment → Purchase Intention			0.106
Perceived Value → Purchase Intention			0.031

Source: Data of Research (2021)

Inner model tests are performed to determine relationships between constructs. The first test, R², indicates how much of the variance of the dependent variable is explained by all independent variables. Whereas the of R² values ranges from 0 – 1. R² values 0.75, 0.5, and 0.25 classified as strong, medium, and weak models. Goodness of Fit Test Result show that R² of purchase intention variables can be said to be moderate because it has less value than 0.67. The R² value of purchase intention is 0.623 or 62.3%, indicating that service quality and store environment can influence purchase intention, while 37.7% can be influenced by other variables not examined. Then, The R² value of perceived value is 0.587 or 58.7%, indicating that service quality and store environment can influence purchase intention, while 41.3% can be influenced by other variables not examined.

The f² (effect size) test was conducted to assess how the removal of the selected exogenous construct affects the R² of the endogenous construct. The result of f² test show the impact of service quality on perceived value have the strongest relationship. While service quality on purchase intention with moderate impact. The moderate impact also on store environment and perceived value with purchase intention. Therefore, this research model is already good to have a medium to strong size effect.

The construct cross-validation redundancy test result shows the test result of the value of Q² = 0.406 on the purchase intention variable. The Q² value of the perceived value variable is 0.367. The computed results show predictions with associated values > 0, so the model is viable and has associated predictors.

Fig 3. Hypothesis Testing Results

Source: Picture of research (2021)

Table 5 Hypothesis Testing Result

No	Hypothesis	Original Sample	Standard Deviation	T-Statistics	P Values	Result
H1	SQ → PV	0.545	0.060	9.162	0.000	Significant Positive
H2	→ PV	0.282	0.066	4.285	0.000	Significant Positive
H3	PV → PI	0.169	0.065	2.615	0.000	Significant Positive
H4	SQ → PI	0.420	0.082	5.094	0.000	Significant Positive
H5	SE → PI	0.289	0.078	3.723	0.000	Significant Positive
H6	SQ → PV → PI	0.092	0.037	2.498	0.013	Significant Positive
H7	SE → PV → PI	0.048	0.023	2.084	0.038	Significant Positive

Source: Data of Research (2021)

➤ *Effect of Service Quality on Perceived Value*

The t-statistic for the relationship between service quality and perceived value is 9.162 (> 1.96), which is statistically significant. The original sample estimate value is positive, 0.545, indicating that the relationship between service quality and perceived value is in a positive direction. This study's H1 hypothesis that service quality has a positive and statistically significant effect on perceived value can therefore be accepted.

The results of testing the hypothesis indicate that service quality has a positive and statistically significant effect on perceived value. This indicates that the higher the perceived value given by customers, the higher the quality of service provided. Customer expectations are significantly influenced by the quality of service. Services that successfully meet customer expectations will have a high perceived value, which makes it crucial to maintain service quality to preserve this perception.

High service quality entails the ability to influence multiple aspects of the service in order to provide consumers with more benefits. During the Covid-19 pandemic, consumers tended to avoid coming to offline stores because they had a high risk of virus transmission. Despite this pandemic, Sociolla continues to open new physical stores. The offline store operations of Sociolla implement a stringent health protocol while still providing consumers with convenience.

This study's findings concur with those of Tushi (2014), which indicate that service quality influences perceived value. In marketing, value is contingent on the commitment to provide superior service, as only superior service can create value for consumers. In his research, Norouzi et al. (2013), demonstrate that perceived value can be derived from functional value, which indicates that services can fulfill functions that create value for consumers.

➤ *Effect of Store Environment on Perceived Value*

With a t-statistic of 4.285 (> 1.96), Table 5 demonstrates that the influence of the store environment on perceived value is significant. The original sample estimate value, 0.282, is positive, indicating that the direction of the relationship between store environment and perceived value is positive. On the basis of this study's H2 hypothesis, it can be concluded that the store environment has a positive and statistically significant effect on perceived value.

The hypothesis testing results indicate that the store environment has a positive and statistically significant effect on perceived value. The store environment plays an important role in an offline store, particularly in creating a favorable impression on consumers when they enter. When choosing a place to simply relax with coworkers, family, etc., consumers also consider the store environment [31].

This study's findings are consistent with those of Hanaysha (2018) who found that the store environment has an effect on perceived value. He added that the store environment is crucial for outlets to make a favorable impression on customers.

➤ *Effect of Perceived Value on Purchase Intention*

The influence of perceived value on purchase intention is statistically significant with a t-statistic of 2.615 (> 1.96), as shown in Table 5. The original sample estimate value is positive, 0.169, indicating that the relationship between perceived value and purchase intention is in a positive direction. Therefore, in this study's H3 it can be concluded that perceived value has a positive and statistically significant effect on purchase intention.

The results of the hypothesis testing indicate that perceived value significantly affects purchase intent. Consumers' values for a product or service can increase their intent to purchase [32]. When consumers place a greater value on a product or service, they are more likely to intend to acquire it.

This study's findings are consistent with those of Peng et al. (2018), who found that perceived value has a significant impact on purchase intent. In addition, Chae et al. (2019) found that the increase in positive emotional value perceptions increases the number of consumers' purchase intentions. The research of Graciola et al. (2020), demonstrates that the perceived value of a product can influence consumers' purchase intentions.

➤ *Effect of Service Quality on Purchase Intention*

According to Table 5, the effect of service quality on purchase intention is statistically significant with a t-statistic of 5.094 (> 1.96). The initial sample estimate is positive, at 0.420, indicating that the direction of the relationship between service quality and purchase intention is positive. On the basis of this study's H4 hypothesis, it is possible to conclude that Service Quality has a positive and statistically significant impact on purchase intention.

The results of a test of hypotheses indicate that service quality has a substantial effect on purchase intent. Consumers' intent to buy can be increased by a quality service. According to Tjiptono (2019), service quality is a dynamic condition involving products and services in addition to processes and the environment that meet or exceed customer expectations. The existence of Sociolla's brick-and-mortar store enables consumers to directly view and acquire beauty care products. Consumers' purchase intentions can be increased by providing superior service that exceeds their expectations.

These findings concur with those of Ahmad & Zhang (2020), Won & Kim (2020) dan Alfatiha & Budiatmo (2020). According to the findings of this study, service quality has a substantial impact on purchase intention.

➤ *Effect of Store Environment on Purchase Intention*

With a t-statistic of 3.723 (> 1.96), Table 5 demonstrates that the influence of the store environment on purchase intention is significant. The original sample estimate is positive, indicating that the direction of the relationship between store environment and purchase intention is positive. This study accepts the H5 hypothesis that the store environment has a positive and statistically significant effect on purchase intention.

The findings of the study indicate that the store environment has a substantial effect on purchase intent. These results demonstrate that a store's ambiance can increase customers' intent to buy. Kotler (2015) as cited in Luniya & Verghese (2017) defines a store atmosphere as to design a buying environment to produce a certain emotional effect on the buyer which increases the probability of his purchase. Hussain & Ali (2015), share the same view that lighting has a substantial positive influence on the purchase intention. Lighting is an important aspect of the ambience factor for store environment, as it influences consumer behavior in the form of mood, purchasing behavior, preferences, approach behaviour, sales, etc.

The findings of this study are consistent with those of Villiers et al. (2018), an environment that encourages customers to remain in the store for longer enables sales representatives to develop stronger relationships with customers, resulting in a greater rate of repeat business from these customers.

➤ *Mediating Effect of Perceived Value*

According to Table 5, the effect of service quality on purchase intention as mediated by perceived value is statistically significant with a t-statistic of 2.49 (> 1.96). The original sample estimate value is positive, at 0.092, indicating that the relationship between service quality and purchase intention is in a positive direction. In this study's H6 it can be concluded that perceived value holds a partial mediating effect between service quality and purchase intention.

The results show that perceived value is able to mediate the effect of service quality on purchase intention. This shows that the value of a product or service can increase the effect of service quality on purchase intention. Customers are more likely to make a purchase if the quality of the service provided by the provider or the quality of the goods or services meets their expectations, as well as if these goods and services are highly rated. According to the research of Graciola et al. (2020), customer service focuses on physical appearance, including clothing, physical attractiveness, demographic issues (such as age, gender, and ethnicity), and nonverbal factors such as smiles, facial expressions, gestures, and other body language that contributes to physical attractiveness. The value perceptions created by the services provided can influence the purchase intentions of customers.

Same as service quality, store environment have influence on purchase intention as mediated by perceived value is statistically significant, the t-statistic of 2.084 (> 1.96). The original sample estimate is positive, indicating that the relationship between the store environment and purchase intention is positive. The store environment has a positive and statistically significant effect on purchase intention, mediated by perceived value, according to hypothesis H7 of this study.

The results of hypothesis testing show that perceived value is able to mediate the effect of the store environment on purchase intention. On the basis of the store's appearance, the customer's perception of the store's values can be constructed. This perception helps the seller increase the customer's purchase intentions.

Hasil pengujian hipotesis menunjukkan bahwa *perceived value* mampu memediasi pengaruh *store environment* terhadap *purchase intention*. Persepsi pelanggan atas nilai-nilai dapat dibangun atas dasar kesadaran akan penampilan toko. Persepsi tersebut membantu pihak penjual untuk meningkatkan niat pembelian pelanggan. Research conducted by Burlison & Oe, (2018) indicates that a store's image can exceed customer expectations, thereby increasing customer intent to purchase. Moreover, store image as a component of the store environment is viewed as a multidimensional concept that relates to multiple aspects of retail stores. Wang (2019), reveals that the factors that can affect a store's image are a combination of tangible and intangible factors.

V. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, this study is assessing several factors that influence purchase intentions at offline store in pandemic era. The results show that service quality, store environment and perceived value positively influence the behavior of purchase intentions at Sociolla Lippo Puri Mall in the future. Perceived value holds a partial mediating effect between service quality and purchase intention. Perceived value also holds a partial mediating effect between store environment and purchase intention.

Ritel sector must continually maintain and improve the quality of products and services offered in offline store areas in order to provide consumers with an experience that cannot be replicated via shopping online. The positive image that a comfortable store environment provides in order to increase its marketing value. Therefore, marketing practitioners should pay attention to the quality of the store environment, the service quality offered, as well as the perceived value in their marketing strategy.

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